

Title: Future of Data Science - its collision course with Artificial Intelligence

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ABSTRACT:

Artificial intelligence (AI), in recent years, has been changing the landscape of most businesses across all major industries. On the other hand, with most conventional data, both in personal and organizational circumstances, gradually transforming into big data, the role of data science within large enterprises has also gained significant attention. While some may consider that AI is changing how data science is leveraged for digital transformation, others may believe that data science is influencing AI change everyday life for the better. So where is the actual boundary between these two rather important fields of scientific interest that foresees them as the new frontiers in the modern information world. Will the rise of AI force data scientists to evolve? Or will proper data science strategy help unlock the complete potential of AI adoption in businesses? Why does it, in this age of analytics and competing world of data-driven business, feel like AI and data science as set to be on a collision course?

In an attempt to delineate the boundary between data science and AI in modern enterprise applications, this presentation will highlight some of the main opportunities and challenges that make these complementary fields of scientific advancements critical towards the future of businesses. In this attempt to resolving the ambiguity in understanding the seemingly nuanced differences between data science and AI from a business perspective, several case studies discussed within this presentation will enable businesses understand their data capacity and the opportunity that data science and AI offer in helping commoditize it for value generation and changing the basis of competition.

KEYWORDS:

Data Science; Artificial Intelligence; Data Strategy; AI Adoption; Analytics; Case Study;

BIOGRAPHY:

Harish is an experienced data officer and an expert in Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered data analytics with 15+ years of demonstrated history of working in aerospace, telecommunication, automotive, security, geospatial and biomedical industries. He is the Director of Artificial Intelligence and Chief Scientist at Linkay Technologies Inc. group of companies headquartered in the USA. Prior to his current role, Harish was engaged on a consulting contract with The Sky Guys/Defiant Labs, Canada, as their Chief Data Scientist. Previously, he was a chief engineer at Samsung Electronics, India and an assistant professor/lead at the Visual Signal Analysis and Processing (VSAP) research center at Khalifa University, UAE. Harish has also worked as a researcher, managing the Research and Development (R&D) of Ministry of Defense (MoD) UK and European Union (EU)-funded projects at Lancaster and Manchester universities UK. Harish is a strong engineering professional with a Ph.D. in Computer Science and an M.Sc. in Autonomous Systems from Loughborough and Exeter universities UK, respectively.

